

Twigitecture: Coco Homes.

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Abstract:

Twigitecture: Coco Homes introduces a groundbreaking approach to sustainable design by utilizing the natural properties of dehusked coconut shells, optimally designed by nature for structural integrity and ecological harmony. Drawing from the MFA II school of design, the concept integrates the principles of MaC (Manifold as Code) and mereotopology, creating multifunctional, geodesic, and stress-optimized architectures. The unique shape of the coconut, with its natural void and biomimetic qualities, forms the foundation of Coco Homes, representing a convergence of organic material use and advanced design theory. The coconut shell, with its egg-like form, aligns with the metaphysical principles of microcosm-macrocosm relationships, providing an ideal structure for energy-efficient, eco-friendly homes. This paper explores how Coco Homes combine traditional wisdom with modern computational design methods, enabling the creation of resilient and sustainable living spaces.

Keywords:

Twigitecture, Coco Homes, coconut shell, sustainable design, MaC (Manifold as Code), MFA II school of design, mereotopology, geodesic design, multifunctional architecture, stress tensor theory, biomimicry, ecological architecture, microcosm-macrocosm relationship.

MaC or Manifold as Code, defines manifolds in mereotopology in the MFA II school of design invented by the author. MFA or multifunctional design is functional semantics theory of geodesic manifoldic design in stress tensor theory and represented in lambdas of HOL and mereotopology of closed form tensor expressions.

Images courtesy: public sources on the web.

The natural shape of a coconut is optimised to a Mereology to optimised strength, to bulk biomass shell material.

a dehusked coconut shell has that egg-like, void shape perfected by natural design to a metaphysics of that microcosm-macrocosm relationship.